

THE INFLUENCE OF THE LEADERSHIP ROLE OF THE SCHOOL PRINCIPAL AND TEACHER PROFESSIONALISM IN IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE OF MATARAM CITY TEACHERS WITH EDUCATIONAL QUALITY MANAGEMENT AS A MEDIATION VARIABLE

Usman Jayadi ¹, Kiki Farida Ferine ²,
Dandan Haryono ³ and Maulana Majied Sumatrani Saragih ⁴

^{1,2} Universitas Pembangunan Panca Budi, Indonesia.

Email: ¹ujayadi@gmail.com, ²kikifarida@dosen.pancabudi.ac.id

³ Universitas Tadulako, Indonesia. Email: dandanharyono@gmail.com

⁴ STKIP Al Maksum Langkat. Email: maulanamajied494@gmail.com

DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.11545657](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11545657)

Abstract

This research aims to describe the influence of the leadership role of school principals and teacher professionalism in improving the performance of teachers in the city of Mataram with education quality management as a mediating variable. In this research the author used quantitative research methods. In this research the author used a Purposive Sampling approach. The data analysis technique is the activity of collecting data from all respondents, grouping them based on criteria, carrying out tests on each variable, and presenting the data after testing. In this research, the author used Partial Least Square (PLS) data analysis techniques. The research results of the first hypothesis were rejected Principal Leadership (X1) noinfluence on Quality Management (Z), the second hypothesis is accepted. Teacher Professionalism (X2) influences Quality Management (Z), the third hypothesis is accepted Principal Leadership (X1),The fourth hypothesis is accepted. Teacher professionalism (X2) has an effect on Teacher Performance (Y),The fifth hypothesis is rejected. Quality Management (Z) has no effect on Teacher Performance (Y), the sixth hypothesis is rejected Principal Leadership (X1) significant effect on Teacher Performance (Y) through Quality Management (Z) and the seventh hypothesis is accepted. Teacher Professionalism (X2) has a significant effect on Teacher Performance (Y) through Quality Management (Z).

Keywords: The Role of Principal Leadership, Teacher Professionalism, Teacher Performance and Quality Management.

INTRODUCTION

Teacher performance is carried out in carrying out duties and responsibilities as an educator at school. Teacher performance according to (Faozan, 2022) is an important element in education. Apart from that, it is also a determinant of the high and low quality of education. Therefore, every teacher must understand the goals of national education, so that every attitude and action in teaching students is directed towards the national education goals that have been formulated. The role of teachers as educators is the main pillar in achieving national education goals. Furthermore, Education System Law Number 20 of 2003 states that the position of teacher as an educator is a professional position which has a central and strategic role in realizing national education goals.

Teacher performance is one of the factors that measures school success. Performance is achievement, work results or performance. The teacher's performance in question is the result of the teacher's work which is reflected in planning, implementing and assessing the process of teaching and learning activities whose intensity is based on the work ethic and professional discipline of the teacher in the

learning process. The work results shown must also be high. The possible factors that can influence teacher performance are the quality of the teacher's knowledge, the amount of compensation received, the level of discipline possessed, work motivation and the work environment in which the teacher teaches. Factors that can influence teacher performance are the quality of teacher knowledge. The quality of knowledge possessed by a teacher does not just exist, but is obtained from a long process of education and learning. The situation of teachers in Mataram City is a concern because most teachers do not have sufficient professionalism to carry out their duties.

In reality, the quality of Mataram City teachers is still worrying. From the teacher competency test of around 100 teachers, the results were not encouraging because most of the scores were below 50 out of the highest score of 100. The Director General of Teachers and Education Personnel said that the UKG results were a real portrait of teacher quality. In reality, the teacher's condition is still difficult. Therefore, the UKG results are an important basis for designing appropriate teacher education and training for each teacher. This shows that the quality of teacher knowledge in Indonesia is still low. This is caused by various factors, some of which are teachers not mastering the material used to teach it to students and many teachers being unable to adapt to the times so that teachers cannot use sophisticated tools such as computers and other tools in learning. .

Increasing teacher performance through providing appropriate compensation and appreciation for the teaching profession is very appropriate, because teachers can meet their needs appropriately and do not need to look for side jobs so they can focus more on their work. By focusing the teacher's attention on work, it will influence the increase in work productivity and the quality of education will also increase. Everyone will definitely work better in the future, if the results of their work are appreciated by getting a salary or service compensation commensurate with their work. Improving teacher performance is the responsibility of the school principal. This improvement is carried out by providing professional assistance services or guidance provided by supervisors, namely supervisors and school principals, to teachers to improve their performance in achieving educational goals.

The low quality of education is related to the policies used by the government so far in developing education, which places more emphasis on the structural dimension with an input-output approach. (Murtafiah, 2022). The government believes that by improving the pattern of implementing integrated quality management with maximum input management, it will automatically be able to improve the quality of output which is expected to be better. The educational process with a macro input-output approach pays less attention to micro aspects, this is what happens in schools, especially in the city of Mataram. In other words, in developing education, apart from using a macro approach, it is also necessary to pay attention to the micro approach, namely by providing a broad focus on school institutions regarding the overall condition of the school, such as the development of school management with integrated quality management in Mataram City.

Based on the results of observations carried out in Mataram City, it shows that the principles of integrated quality management have begun to be implemented. However, there are several factors that hinder the application of this principle, namely the quality of human resources. The quality of human resources is closely related to education. For this reason, improving the quality of education is a process that is integrated with

the process of improving the quality of human resources. The participation of the community, especially parents of students, in providing education has so far been limited to financial support. Even though their role is very important in the decision-making, monitoring and evaluation process. There is also a lack of awareness among students, there are still many students who still like to break the rules. For example, there are students who are late for school and often miss school. However, the school has made several efforts to overcome these obstacles, but they are not optimal enough. Therefore, the application of integrated quality management principles must have supporters who work together to improve schools, so that schools can be further improved to become even better schools, especially in Mataram City now and in the future.

School principals must prepare various strategies to be able to develop a curriculum that suits the needs of the school. They also need to create a conducive atmosphere to foster enthusiasm and develop students' learning motivation. (Ideswal, Yahya, & Alkadri, 2020). In his research (Abriyanto, Liswara Neneng, 2022) explained that school progress lies in the principal's leadership style which makes a big contribution to the school. Principal leadership style (Cicilia Tri Suci Rokhani, 2020) contribute to determining school performance. The principal has an important role in improving teacher performance discipline. School principals must have emotional intelligence that is able to instill, promote and improve mental, moral, physical and artistic values in teachers, administrative staff and students. The role of the school principal must show a persuasive and exemplary attitude so that he can be an example of teacher performance discipline. Principals who do not want to hear the opinions of subordinates cause teachers to act a priori in the interests of work or school. This will reduce teacher work discipline. Trust in teachers needs to be instilled so that teachers have responsibility in their work so that teacher performance discipline will be achieved.

Teacher professionalism according to (Rifa'i, M., Muadin, A., Faiz, F., Khomsiyah, L., & Mabruroh, 2022). Teacher professionalism is a teacher's expertise who has a deep understanding of pedagogical or academic background, knowledge of pedagogical theory, and the ability to carry out pedagogical theory. In order to increase the professionalism of teaching staff, it is influenced by many factors, including the leadership role of the principal, because the principal has a very important role in managing teacher activities, learning activities, and the principal is also directly tasked with implementing all types and forms of policies and regulations. which all teaching staff and students wish to comply with. Professional teachers are not only required to understand all fields of science, subject matter, to motivate students, have high skills and broad knowledge, but also have a good understanding of living things and people. The nature of this substance will underlie the thinking and work traditions of teaching staff, and their loyalty to the agency's profession. Then another phenomenon found in this school is that there are still teachers who teach not according to their field of expertise. So the ability of teachers to teach is less professional and educators have not yet improved programs and creative methods of teaching and learning activities so as to encourage students' interest and motivation to be active in teaching and learning activities.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Teacher Performance

(Darmadi, 2018) Teacher performance is the ability demonstrated by teachers in carrying out their duties or work. Performance is said to be good and satisfactory if the goals achieved are in accordance with the standards that have been set. According to (Barnawi, & Arifin, 2017). Teacher performance can be interpreted as the level of success of teachers in carrying out their duties and education in accordance with their responsibilities and authority based on performance standards that have been set during a certain period within the framework of achieving educational goals. Teacher performance can be seen and measured based on the competency specifications that each teacher must have. (Abas, 2017) said that teacher performance is all the activities carried out in carrying out their mandate and responsibility in educating, teaching and guiding, directing and guiding students in achieving their level of maturity and maturity.

Education Quality Management

Education quality management is an education management effort that has established standardization of the education system based on quality assessment. (Arinda, 2018) Quality management is a management effort to direct and control an organization/institution in determining policies, targets, plans and quality processes/procedures for achieving quality on an ongoing basis. (Dalmeri, 2016) The aim of quality management is to ensure conformity between the process and the resulting output which will provide satisfaction and continuous improvement in the quality of education. Efforts to improve the quality of education in question are not done all at once, but rather are based on improving the quality of each component of education.

Principal Leadership

Principal leadership is leadership that focuses on curriculum and learning development, staff development, learning supervision, learning programs, evaluating teacher and student programs, action research, preparing organizational resources, and continuously improving the quality of learning outcomes and processes. According to (Yukl, 2010) The definition of leadership reflects the assumption that leadership is related to the deliberate process of a person to exert a strong influence on others to guide, structure, facilitate activities and relationships within a group or organization.

Teacher Professionalism

Teacher professionalism is proven by their competence which creates performance that can support the quality of education. (Priansa, 2017) Professionalism is characterized by quality and pride in the profession in which they are assigned. The sense of pride possessed by a teacher results in high dedication to the tasks carried out. For this reason, the professionalism of a teacher is important for every teacher to have. Professionalism is characterized by quality and pride in the profession in which they are assigned. The sense of pride possessed by a teacher results in high dedication to the tasks carried out. For this reason, the professionalism of a teacher is important for every teacher to have.

Conceptual framework

Conceptual framework acc (Sugiyono, 2014) is a theoretical relationship between research variables, namely, between the independent variable and the dependent

variable which will be observed or measured through research. The conceptual framework in this research is as an instrument to be able to describe and explain the phenomena that occur.

Figure 1: Conceptual Framework

Hypothesis

Based on the research framework and paradigm on the previous page, the researcher formulated the following hypothesis:

1. The principal's leadership influences quality management.
2. Teacher professionalism influences quality management.
3. Quality management influences teacher performance.
4. The principal's leadership influences teacher performance.
5. Teacher professionalism influences teacher performance.
6. The principal's leadership influences teacher performance with quality management as a mediating variable.
7. Teacher professionalism influences teacher performance with quality management as a mediating variable.

RESEARCH METHODS

Types of Research

In this research the author used quantitative research methods. According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Quantitative research is a research method based on the philosophy of positivism to examine a certain population or sample, and sampling is carried out randomly by collecting data using instruments, as well as statistical data analysis. The quantitative research paradigm is considered as a causal relationship between research variables.

Research Sample

A sample is a group whose number is relatively smaller than the population selected and used for research (Alvi, 2016). In this research the author uses a purposive sampling approach, namely a sampling technique that is based on certain characteristics and has a close relationship to the required population. (Margono, 2021). Thus, the number of samples required for this research was 97 respondents.

Data analysis method

According to (Sugiyono, 2018) Data analysis techniques are the activity of collecting data from all respondents, grouping them based on criteria, carrying out tests on each variable, and presenting the data after testing. In this research, the author used Partial Least Square (PLS) data analysis techniques. PLS is a statistical data analysis method that analyzes independent (exogenous) variables and dependent (endogenous) variables simultaneously (Ghozali, 2015).

Hypothesis test

Hypothesis testing is carried out to determine whether there is a direct and indirect (partial or simultaneous) influence on exogenous (free) variables on endogenous (dependent) variables. With a significance or alpha level of 5% (0.05) to accept or reject a hypothesis statistically.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

The measurement model (outer model) is confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) by testing the validity and reliability of latent constructs. The following are the results of the outer model evaluation in this research.

Validity test

This research uses help from Smart PLS 3.0 software. To test the validity of data, it can be used to test the validity of data. Convergent validity can be used to look at the loading factor value and discriminant validity by looking at the cross loading value.

Figure 2: Outer Model

1. Convergent Validity

Convergent validity of the measurement model with the reflective indicator model is assessed based on the correlation between the item score/component score and the construct score calculated using PLS. Based on Figure 4.1 above, it can be seen that all loading factor values have exceeded the limit of 0.7, so it can be concluded that each indicator in this study is valid. Therefore, these indicators can be used to measure research variables.

2. Discriminant Validity

Discriminant validity compares the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value of each construct with the correlation between other constructs in the model. Based on Figure 4.1 above, it can be seen that all cross loading values for each of the indicators targeted have a higher correlation with each variable compared to other variables. It can be concluded that the indicators above are valid as a whole.

Reliability Test

An instrument can be said to be reliable by looking at the value of Average Variance Extracted more than 0.5, Cronbach Alpha more than 0.6 and Composite Reliability more than 0.7.

Table 1: Calculation of AVE, Cronbach Alpha, and Composite Reliability

	<i>Cronbach's Alpha</i>	<i>rho_A</i>	<i>Composite Reliability</i>	<i>Average Variance Extracted (AVE)</i>
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.892	0.914	0.894	0.635
Quality Management (Z)	0.920	0.925	0.920	0.699
Principal Leadership (X1)	0.887	0.894	0.889	0.618
Teacher Professionalism (X2)	0.921	0.927	0.922	0.705

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Based on Table 4.1 above, it can be seen that the Cronbach Alpha value of the variable Teacher Performance (Y) of 0.892, Quality Management variable (Z) of 0.920, variable Principal Leadership (X1) of 0.887 and the Teacher Professionalism variable (X2) of 0.921. From the results of the calculations above, it can be seen that all indicators are reliable in measuring the latent variables.

Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Evaluation of the inner model can be seen from several indicators which include the coefficient of determination (R²), Predictive Relevance (Q²) and Goodness of Fit Index (GoF) (Hussein, 2015). The results of the structural model displayed by Smart PLS 3.0 in this research are as follows:

Figure 3: Structural Model (Inner Model)

R2 Results (R-square)

In assessing the model with PLS, start by looking at the R-square for each dependent latent variable. The results of the r2 calculation in this study are as follows:

Table 2: Correlation Value (r2)

	<i>R-square</i>	<i>Adjusted R-square</i>
Teacher Performance (Y)	0.892	0.914
Quality Management (Z)	0.920	0.925

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Based on the results of calculations using bootstrapping in Table 2 above, it is known that the r2 value of the Quality Management (Z) variable is 0.925, which means that the Quality Management (Z) variable is influenced by the variable Principal Leadership (X1) and the Teacher Professionalism variable (X2) is 92.5% or in other words variable contribution Principal Leadership (X1) and the Teacher Professionalism variable (X2) was 92.5%.

The r2 result of the variable Teacher Performance (Y) of 0.914 which means that the variable Teacher Performance (Y) influenced by Principal Leadership (X1), variable Teacher Professionalism (X2) and Quality Management (Z) amounted to 91.4% or in other words variable contribution Principal Leadership (X1), variable Teacher Professionalism (X2) and Quality Management (Z) were 91.4%.

Goodness of Fit Model

Goodness of fit calculations can be used to determine the magnitude of the contribution made by exogenous variables to endogenous variables. The GoF value

in PLS analysis can be calculated using Q-square predictive relevance (Q²). The following are the results of the Goodness of Fit Model calculations in this research:

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - r_{12}) (1 - r_{22})$$

$$Q^2 = 1 - (1 - 0.925) (1 - 0.914)$$

$$Q^2 = 0.9935$$

Based on the calculation above, the Q-square predictive relevance (Q²) value is 0.9935 or 99.35%. This is able to show that the diversity of variables Teacher Performance (Y) able to explain the model as a whole is 0.9935 or it can also be interpreted as the contribution of the variables Principal Leadership (X1), variable Teacher Professionalism (X2) and Quality Management (Z) on variables Teacher Performance (Y) overall it is 99.35%, while the remaining 0.65% is the contribution of variables not discussed in this study.

Hypothesis test

Based on the results of the outer model carried out, all the hypotheses tested have met the requirements, so they can be used as analysis models in this research. Hypothesis testing in this study uses an alpha of 5%, which means that the t-statistic value is ≥ 2.048 or the probability value is $\leq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). The limit of 0.05 means that the probability of deviation is only 5% and the remaining 95% is indicated as being able to accept the hypothesis.

Hypothesis testing in this research is divided into two parts, namely direct influence testing and indirect influence testing (mediation). Testing the direct effect will use bootstrapping in Smart PLS 3.0 software, while testing the indirect effect will use t-statistics on the indirect effect.

Table 4: Path Coefficients

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>Q statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
Principal Leadership (X1)-> Quality Management (Z)	0.133	0.208	0.184	0.136	0.471
Teacher Professionalism (X2) -> Quality Management (Z)	0.787	0.730	0.175	5,049	0,000
Principal Leadership (X1)->Teacher Performance (Y)	0.522	0.548	0.176	2,219	0.003
Teacher Professionalism (X2)->Teacher Performance (Y)	0.577	0.584	0.200	3,064	0.004
Quality Management (Z) ->Teacher Performance (Y)	-0.102	-0.132	0.176	1,507	0.564

Source: Primary data processed (2024)

Based on Table 4, the test results for each hypothesis are as follows:

a. Principal Leadership (X1) influence on Quality Management (Z).

Based on the test results in Table 4.3, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variables Principal Leadership (X1) on the Quality Management variable (Z) is 0.136 with sig. of 0.471. The test results show that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the first hypothesis is rejected.

b. Teacher Professionalism (X2) influence on Quality Management (Z).

Based on the test results in Table 4.3, it can be seen that the t-statistical value of the relationship between the Teacher Professionalism variable (X2) and the Quality Management variable (Z) is 5.049 with sig. equal to 0.000. The test results show that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig value. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the second hypothesis is accepted.

c. Principal Leadership (X1) influence on Teacher Performance (Y).

Based on the test results in Table 4.3, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variables Principal Leadership (X1) to variables Teacher Performance (Y) is 2.219 with sig. of 0.003. The test results show that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the third hypothesis is accepted.

d. Teacher Professionalism (X2) influence on Teacher Performance (Y).

Based on the test results contained in Table 4.3, it can be seen that the t-statistical value of the relationship between the Teacher Professionalism variable (X2) and the variable Teacher Performance (Y) is 3,064 with sig. of 0.004. The test results show that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the fourth hypothesis is accepted.

e. Quality Management (Z) has an effect on Teacher Performance (Y).

Based on the test results contained in Table 4.3, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between the Quality Management variable (Z) and the variable Teacher Performance (Y) is 1.507 with sig. of 0.564. The test results show that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the fifth hypothesis is rejected.

Indirect Effect Testing

The indirect influence test is carried out by testing the strength of the indirect influence of the independent variable (variable an indirect influence can be declared significant if both direct influences that form it are significant. The results of this test can be seen in the following table:

Table 5: Indirect Effect

	<i>Original Sample (O)</i>	<i>Sample Mean (M)</i>	<i>Standard Deviation (STDEV)</i>	<i>Q statistics (O/STDEV)</i>	<i>P Values</i>
Principal Leadership (X1)-> Quality Management (Z) ->Teacher Performance (Y)	0.135	0.186	0.172	0.782	0.434
Teacher Professionalism (X2)-> Quality Management (Z) ->Teacher Performance (Y)	0.514	0.405	0.200	2,574	0.001

a. Principal Leadership (X1) significant effect on Teacher Performance (Y) through Quality Management (Z). Based on the test results in Table 4.4, it can be seen that the t-statistic value of the relationship between variables Principal Leadership (X1) to variables Teacher Performance (Y) through variables Quality Management (Z) is 0.782 with sig. of 0.434. The test results show that the t-statistic is ≥ 1.96 and the sig. $\leq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus, the sixth hypothesis is rejected.

- b. Teacher Professionalism (X2) significant effect on Teacher Performance (Y) through Quality Management (Z). Based on the test results contained in Table 4.4, it can be seen that the t-statistical value of the relationship between the Teacher Professionalism variable (X2) and the variable Teacher Performance (Y) through variables Quality Management (Z) is 2.574 with sig. of 0.001. The test results show that the t-statistic is ≥ 1.96 and the sig. $\leq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the seventh hypothesis is accepted.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the research and discussion in the previous chapter, it can be concluded as follows:

1. Test result Principal Leadership (X1) influence on Quality Management (Z) shows that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig value. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the first hypothesis is rejected.
2. The results of testing Teacher Professionalism (X2) have an effect on Quality Management (Z) showing that the t-statistic is ≤ 1.96 and the sig. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the second hypothesis is accepted.
3. Test result Principal Leadership (X1) influence on Teacher Performance (Y). shows that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig value. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the third hypothesis is accepted.
4. The results of the Teacher Professionalism test (X2) have an effect on Teacher Performance (Y). shows that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig value. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the fourth hypothesis is accepted.
5. Quality Management (Z) test results have an effect on Teacher Performance (Y). shows that the t-statistic ≤ 1.96 and the sig value. $\geq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the fifth hypothesis is rejected.
6. Test result Principal Leadership (X1) significant effect on Teacher Performance (Y) through Quality Management (Z). shows that the t-statistic ≥ 1.96 and the sig value. $\leq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the sixth hypothesis is rejected.
7. The results of the Teacher Professionalism test (X2) have a significant effect on Teacher Performance (Y) through Quality Management (Z). shows that the t-statistic ≥ 1.96 and the sig value. $\leq$ level of significance ($\alpha = 5\%$). Thus the seventh hypothesis is accepted.

Bibliography

- 1) Abas, E. (2017). Magnet Kepemimpinan Kepala Madrasah Terhadap Kinerja. Guru. Jakarta: PT Elex Media Komputindo.
- 2) Abriyanto, Liswara Neneng, & Y. E. G. (2022). Pengembangan LKS Blended Learning Berbasis Web Pada Materi Pencemaran Lingkungan Untuk Meningkatkan Keterampilan Proses Sains. *Journal of Environment and Management*, 3(1), 26–34.
- 3) Alvi, M. (2016). A Manual for Selecting Sampling Techniques in Research. Munich. Personal. RePEc. Archive.
- 4) Arinda, F. (2018). Implementasi Manajemen Berbasis Sekolah. Dalam Meningkatkan Prestasi Belajar Siswa. Yogyakarta: CV. Gre Publishing.
- 5) Barnawi, & Arifin, M. (2017). Kinerja Guru Profesional. Yogyakarta: Ar-. Ruzz Media.

- 6) Cicilia Tri Suci Rokhani. (2020). Pengaruh Gaya Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah Terhadap Kinerja Sekolah di SDN Dengkek 01 Pati, dalam *Journal Industrial Engineering & Management Research (JIEMAR)* Vol. 1 No. 2.
- 7) Dalmeri. (2016). *Islamic Quality Education Management*. Jakarta: PT. Gramedia Pustaka Utama.
- 8) Darmadi. (2018). *Manajemen Sumber Daya Manusia Kekepalasekolahan "Melejitkan Produktivitas Kerja Kepala Sekolah dan Faktor-Faktor yang Memengaruhi"*. Yogyakarta: Deepublish.
- 9) Faozan, A. (2022). *Peningkatan Kinerja Guru Pendidikan Agama Islam melalui Supervisi Akademik, Diklat, dan Partisipasi dalam Kelompok Kerja Guru*. Serang: Penerbit A-Empat.
- 10) Ghozali, I. dan H. L. (2015). *Partial Least Squares Konsep Teknik dan Aplikasi dengan Program Smart PLS 3.0*. Semarang: Universitas Diponegoro Semarang.
- 11) Ideswal, Yahya, & Alkadri, H. (2020). Kontribusi Iklim Sekolah dan Kepemimpinan Kepala Sekolah terhadap Kinerja Guru Sekolah Dasar. *Jurnal Basicedu*, 4(2), 460-466. DOI: 10.31004/basicedu.v4i2.381.
- 12) Kusumawaty, I., Noviadi, P., Cahyati, P., & Jayadi, U. (2022). Experience of Victims Bullying Among School Students with Dormitory Facilities. *Eurasian Journal of Educational Research*, 99(99), 219-232.
- 13) Margono. (2021). *Metodologi Penelitian Pendidikan*. Jakarta: Rineka Cipta.
- 14) Murtafiah, N. H. (2022). Implementasi Manajemen. *Pembiayaan Pendidikan*. *Unisan Jurnal*, 1(3), 347-354.
- 15) Priansa, D. (2017). *Manajemen Pelayanan Prima*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 16) Rifa'i, M., Muadin, A., Faiz, F., Khomsiyah, L., & Mabruroh, A. (2022). Menciptakan Pembelajaran Efektif melalui Penguatan Komitmen Guru PAUD. *Jurnal Obsesi : Jurnal Pendidikan Anak Usia Dini*, 6(4), 3739–3746.
- 17) Sugiyono. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Pendidikan Pendekatan Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*. Bandung: Alfabeta.
- 18) Sugiyono. (2018). *Metode Penelitian Kuantitatif, Kualitatif, dan R&D*, penerbit. Alfabeta, Bandung.
- 19) Yukl, G. (2010). *Leadership in Organizations (7th edition)*. Jakarta: PT. Indeks.